

LITERATURE REVIEW OF DEVELOPMENT OF AN EFFICIENT SENTIMENT ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK USING ADAPTIVE DILATED DENSE GRU WITH WORD EMBEDDING AND PRE-PROCESSING PROCEDURES

P.Saravanan¹, Dr.M.Sundara Rajan²

¹Research Scholar, PG and Research Department of Computer Science, Government Arts College, Nandanam, Chennai-35, India

¹sharandwh@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, PG and Research Department of Computer Science, Government Arts College, Nandanam, Chennai-35, India

²drmsrajan23@yahoo.com

Received: 22nd Oct 2025 / Accepted : 29th Oct 2025 ,

© ICIAET 2025

Abstract

In today's digital era, Sentiment Analysis(SA) has been a prominent area of study within Natural Language Processing (NLP) in the current digital era. Sentiment analysis's main objective is to recognize and analyze the feelings and viewpoints that users convey through textual data. Sentiment analysis is still a difficult and dynamic problem despite a great deal of research and the use of numerous models. Slang, regional accents, grammatical flaws, and spelling mistakes are among the main causes of this. A thorough literature an overview of about 26 recent research that investigate SA utilizing various machine learning methods and datasets is presented in this paper. The review begins by outlining the key contributions of each research study, highlighting the machine learning various techniques employed and the nature of the datasets used. Additionally, it examines the experimental environments and performance metrics reported in these works. The literature review concludes by identifying existing research gaps and ongoing challenges in the field. These insights are intended to guide future research efforts, particularly toward underexplored applications where sentiment analysis can have the most impact.

Keywords—Sentiment analysis (SA), Application-oriented Analysis, Text Analysis, Word Embedding phase, Machine Learning, Performance Analysis, Research Gaps and Challenges.

1. INTRODUCTION

A technique used in Natural Language Processing (NLP) to identify the emotions or sentiments in a document is sentiment

analysis, also known as opinion mining [9]. By examining word choices and context, it is possible to determine whether the tone is neutral, negative, or positive [10]. This technique is commonly used to study customer reviews, social media posts, public opinion about brands, and political discussions [11]. There are different ways to do sentiment analysis, including machine learning, word-based methods, and a mix of both . However, it's not always easy to get accurate results, especially when people use sarcasm, complex language, or when the meaning depends on the situation [12]. Even with these challenges, sentiment analysis is very useful for improving chatbot conversations, understanding customer opinions, and helping businesses make better decisions [13]. More powerful models such as transformers especially BERT and GPT can catch subtle changes in meaning and understand how words relate to each other in a sentence . These advanced techniques are better at dealing with tricky language, such as sarcasm, unclear phrases, and long sentences, making sentiment analysis more accurate and flexible [14]. They are frequently used in areas such as market trend prediction, customer feedback, and social media analysis.

Machine learning models including Naïve Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest, and Maximum Entropy are frequently used in SA by conventional methods [15]. These models are commonly used to categorize text into categories such as positive, negative, or neutral. Another common approach is the lexicon-based method, which uses predefined lists of

words labeled with a certain sentiment [16]. Words in these lists are considered either positive or negative based on their typical usage. These traditional methods usually require a lot of manual effort. For example, they often depend on counting how many times certain words appear in the text [17]. They also need people to define rules or choose features that help the model understand the sentiment. While these techniques work well for basic sentiment tasks, they have several weaknesses when the language becomes more complex or subtle. The inability of conventional models to identify sarcasm is a significant issue [18]. Additionally, they struggle with words whose meaning varies depending on the situation. For instance, depending on how it is used, the meaning of "sick" may indicate "ill" or "awesome." These models also find it hard to understand unclear or vague expressions. Another big challenge is dealing with long sentence, especially when the meaning depends on words that are far apart. Because of these challenges, traditional methods may not give accurate results for texts with emotional depth or complex grammar [19]. They are not as good at capturing the full meaning of a sentence or paragraph. As a result, they are less reliable for analyzing detailed opinions or feelings. This is why deep learning models are now often preferred [20]. They can understand context better, work well with long texts, and deliver more precise results in modern SA tasks.

Deep Learning(DL) has significantly improved SA by addressing many of the challenges faced by older techniques [21]. Traditional methods often struggle with understanding complex language features like sarcasm, confusing expressions, and long, complex sentences. These older models are also limited in how well they can interpret words that depend on context or subtle emotional shifts, making them less accurate. Nevertheless, Deep Learning(DL) algorithms can recognize patterns in text without requiring the extraction of features by hand. They are therefore far more effective and efficient since they are able to automatically recognize the essential elements that determine sentiment [22]. Even when the words are dispersed or the sentence structure is complex, models like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) excel at comprehending the flow of words in a sentence. The ability of these models to handle sequential data makes them excellent at processing long sentences or paragraphs. This is further enhanced by more sophisticated models, such as transformers (like BERT and GPT). These models are made to comprehend every word's complete context in relation to every other word in a sentence [23]. As a result, they are more adept at capturing subtle meanings, including sarcasm or subtle emotional tones. Additionally, deep learning approaches are more adept at determining the connections between distant words in a text, something that conventional approaches frequently fail to do [24]. As a result, when it comes to challenging sentiment analysis tasks, deep learning models yield more accurate and

consistent findings. These sophisticated models are now frequently employed in practical applications, including market trend prediction, social media conversation monitoring, and consumer feedback analysis. They can assist companies in better comprehending the thoughts, feelings, and preferences of their clients, which can result in more intelligent choices and successful tactics [25]. Furthermore, deep learning models are always evolving, becoming more adept at managing a wide range of languages, dialects, and informal speech. In general, deep learning has improved sentiment analysis's strength, flexibility, and applicability across a wide range of businesses, offering insightful information about people's feelings and viewpoints.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 RELATED WORKS

In order to improve the detection and interpretation of user emotions, Mu et al. [1] introduced a unique DIBTBL model in 2024 that included Deep Learning(DL) techniques, an improved swarm intelligence algorithm, and an enlarged sentiment lexicon. The researchers first enriched the sentiment dictionary to extract emotional keywords from review texts. These keywords were then embedded using BERT and mapped into a high-dimensional semantic space, enabling more expressive representations and better sentiment classification. A TextCNN-BiLSTM model was designed to capture both local and global textual features effectively. To optimize this feature extraction model, an improved swarm intelligence algorithm, BWO, was employed. Finally, sentiment classification was performed using an MLP. Comparative experiments demonstrated that the proposed approach achieved higher accuracy than traditional techniques. It achieved an average accuracy improvement of 8.21%, outperforming all competitors when tested against seven sophisticated models on an open dataset. By providing precise insights into user sentiment, the model helped businesses better understand and meet client wants.

The pre-trained BERT-large-cased (BLC) model for dataset training was part of the integrated framework that Durga and Godavarthi [2] presented in 2023. 24 layers, 1024 hidden units, 16 attention heads, and 340 million parameters made up the BLC architecture. The pre-trained BERT model was fine-tuned for sentiment analysis tasks utilizing optimization strategies like SGD. Tokenization and stop-word removal were part of the pre-processing, which was followed by word embedding techniques including Word2Vec and feature extraction using Bag-of-Words (BoW). Based on a model driven by aspects and priorities, a deep sentiment analysis (DSA) classifier was created. This system integrated a Decision-based Recurrent Neural Network (D-RNN) with

Aspect and Priority-based Sentiment Analysis. Confusion matrices were used to assess performance on Twitter, Restaurant, and Laptop datasets that were acquired from Kaggle. The suggested model, which was implemented in Python using libraries like Keras and Pandas, proved to be more successful than previous methods. In order to extract sentiment and thematic information from literary texts, Yu and Qi [3] introduced a hybrid deep learning model in 2025 that integrated Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) networks with an attention mechanism. The model identified subtle emotional and thematic patterns by processing sequences both forward and backward. It was able to concentrate on the most relevant textual elements because to the attention mechanism. To increase efficiency, the Improved Particle Swarm Optimization (IPSO) technique was used to optimize hyperparameters. The model's efficacy was validated by a case study including 500 English novels from various genres. It outperformed conventional CNN-based techniques with high accuracy and F1 scores. Prominent emotional themes including happiness, fear, and grief were identified by the research, along with thematic components like love, treachery, and retaliation. The results indicated future study options, such as multimodal data integration and wider applications in the humanities, and demonstrated the promise of deep learning for improving literary interpretation.

Using the LSTM method, Valarmathi et al. [4] presented a sentiment analysis model for COVID-19-related Twitter data in 2024. The tweets were cleaned using a specialized pre-processing pipeline that made use of Python's Neat Text module. The proposed cleaning module was used to process the 179,177 COVID-19-related tweets in the dataset, and LSTM was used for analysis. The model outperformed a previous Artificial Neural Network (ANN) technique, which obtained 76% accuracy, with a 96% accuracy rate. During significant international events like the COVID-19 pandemic, the study emphasized the significance of efficient pre-processing and LSTM-based modeling in deriving significant insights from extensive textual data.

In order to address a low-resource language environment, Mahmud et al. [5] presented a benchmark dataset for Cricket Sentiment Analysis on Bangla social media postings in 2024. To guarantee comprehensive coverage of user sentiments, the dataset was painstakingly assembled from multiple social media platforms. A Cohen's Kappa value of 0.97 indicated high annotation reliability. Traditional machine learning models performed badly, according to experimental results, with an RNN reaching an accuracy of 0.5239. Deep learning techniques like LSTM and BiLSTM, on the other hand, produced noticeably higher accuracies of 0.897 and 0.952, respectively. These results offered a useful tool for low-resource sentiment analysis research and showed how

well deep learning captures complex attitudes in Bangla cricket conversations.

A approach that uses Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) to produce contextualized text representations based on word position and sentence context was presented by Murfi et al. [6] in 2024. The work used BERT embeddings for Indonesian sentiment analysis, expanding on previous hybrid deep learning techniques. According to simulation results, BERT representations improved all hybrid architectures' performance, with the BERT-based LSTM-CNN model attaining the best accuracy.

In 2024, Thomas and Jeba [7] developed a product recommendation framework that combined sentiment analysis with collaborative filtering. Sentiment classification was carried out using an LSTM-based model. Two collaborative filtering-based recommendation systems were designed, and a similarity-aware (SA) model was integrated with the most effective system to improve recommendation quality. Experimental findings showed that the proposed framework outperformed existing recommendation approaches, demonstrating the advantages of combining sentiment analysis with similarity-aware collaborative filtering to enhance customer satisfaction in e-commerce platforms.

A thorough comparison of deep learning models, such as CNN, RNN, and BiLSTM architectures, for sentiment analysis was carried out in 2024 by Bellar et al. [8]. Several word embedding methods, including Word2Vec, FastText, and BERT and its variations, were used to assess these models. Two classification settings—five-class and three-class sentiment categorization—were used for the evaluation. The study examined performance metrics across models and embeddings using a dataset of customer reviews from an online women's clothing business, offering a thorough assessment of neural network-based methods for sentiment prediction.

3. PROBLEM DEFINITION

One method for figuring out the emotional tone of a text's many components is called aspect-level sentiment analysis (SA). It is essential for analyzing public opinion, customer reviews, and user behavior. Traditional models such as Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and logistic regression rely on manually engineered features. However, these approaches often struggle to capture subtleties like sarcasm, contextual meaning, and complex linguistic structures. Consequently, their accuracy and ability to

generalize in real-world scenarios are restricted. Furthermore, they typically require substantial domain expertise for effective feature engineering and are unable to keep pace with evolving language patterns and slang. The sentiment analysis models currently in use are presented in Table 1.

Sentiment analysis struggles with context, sarcasm, slang, and subtle emotions, which traditional methods often can't handle well. These methods rely on manual features that may miss key details. Deep learning models like LSTMs and transformers solve this by learning patterns automatically and understanding context more accurately.

In previous models, sentiment analysis struggles to understand word relationships, context, and meanings. Traditional methods treat words individually, causing issues with synonyms, multiple meanings, and rare words. Word embeddings solve this by turning words into numbers that capture their relationships. This improves the accuracy of sentiment analysis by better-understanding word connections.

Sentiment analysis with deep learning has challenges like needing large datasets and high computational power. Models can also overfit with small data and struggle with long or complex texts. To solve this, techniques like transfer learning and pre-trained models, such as BERT and GPT, are used. These methods help improve accuracy while reducing the need for massive data and resources.

In sentiment analysis, it can be hard for models to understand long or complicated sentences and the full meaning behind them. Regular deep learning often misses important details, which lowers the accuracy of the results. This makes it tough to catch subtle or complex emotions in text. Adaptive deep learning techniques help fix these problems by better-capturing context and improving how well the model understands sentiment.

Hence a well-advanced deep learning approach will be developed for sentiment analysis.

Table.1. Features and challenges of existing sentiment analysis models.

<p>Mu <i>et al.</i> [1]</p>	<p>DIBTBL</p>	<p>Effective at capturing both short-term and long-term relationships in sequences. Flexible for different types of sequence-based tasks.</p>	<p>It needs large datasets to avoid under fitting and learn meaningful patterns. It has complex hyper parameter tuning.</p>
<p>Durga and Godavarthi [2]</p>	<p>BLC</p>	<p>Excels in sequence-based tasks like sentiment analysis and text classification. Improves prediction accuracy by considering the entire context of the sequence.</p>	<p>Prone to over fitting with large parameter sets, especially on small datasets. Limited interpretability as it's difficult to understand how decisions are made.</p>

Author [citation]	Methodology	Features	Challenges
-------------------	-------------	----------	------------

<p>Yu and Qi [3]</p>	<p>IPSO</p>	<p>Simple to implement with no complex mathematical computation s required. Faster convergence compared to traditional Particle Swarm Optimization .</p>	<p>High computational cost for large and complex optimization problems. May struggle with non-continuous or noisy data, reducing efficiency in certain problem types.</p>	<p>Mahmud <i>et al.</i> [5]</p>	<p>BiLSTM</p>	<p>Improves accuracy in tasks like sentiment analysis and text classification . Flexible and can be used for both classification and regression problems.</p>	<p>Higher computational cost due to processing data in both directions. Requires more memory to store the extra parameters needed for bidirectional processing.</p>
<p>Valarmathi <i>et al.</i> [4]</p>	<p>LSTM</p>	<p>Learns long-term dependencies by remembering past information in sequences. Flexible model that can be used for both classification and regression tasks.</p>	<p>Requires a lot of computation because of its complex structure. Takes longer to train compared to simpler models.</p>	<p>Murfi <i>et al.</i> [6]</p>	<p>BERT</p>	<p>Handles complex language tasks effectively, including question answering and text generation. Fine-tuning is easy for specific tasks like sentiment analysis or text classification .</p>	<p>High computational cost, requiring significant memory and processing power. Long training times for fine-tuning due to the model's large size.</p>

Thomas and Jeba [7]	CF	It does not require domain knowledge or content data. Works well with complex, abstract preferences.	Struggles with data sparsity in large systems. Needs large amounts of user interaction data.
Bellar <i>et al.</i> [8]	CNN	Highly effective for image and visual data processing. Automatically extracts relevant features from raw data.	Needs large labelled datasets for effective training. Requires high computational power and memory.

feelings. Interpreting emotional expressions in user feedback is an important and challenging task for businesses. Conducting text sentiment analysis is highly valuable. Therefore, to address various challenges that exist in traditional methods, a new deep learning-based sentiment analysis framework will be introduced in this proposal. In the first step, essential text data will be collected from standard sources and processed during the text preprocessing phase. Then, the processed text will be passed to the word embedding stage, where spatial-context group attention-based bidirectional encoder representations from transformers (SCGA-BERT) will be used to capture the meaning and relationships between words. Following this, the word embedding results will be sent to the sentiment analysis stage, which will be carried out using an Adaptive Dilated Dense Gated Recurrent Unit (ADD-GRU). To improve the performance of the proposed framework, several parameters in ADD-GRU will be optimized using an enhanced version of the American Zebra Optimization Algorithm (AZOA) [26]. Finally, more accurate results from the sentiment analysis will be obtained from ADD-GRU, and various experiments will be conducted on the developed framework compared to traditional techniques to evaluate its effectiveness. The structure of the sentiment analysis model is presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Structural view of developed sentimental analysis model

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sentiment Analysis (SA), also referred to as emotion analysis, is a fundamental technique in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and plays a vital role in text analysis. Its primary objective is to detect and categorize the emotions expressed in written content as positive, negative, or neutral. This process involves the computational evaluation of opinions and emotional expressions within text. Sentiment analysis can be applied to various textual forms, including full documents as well as individual sentences. It is crucial for organizations to understand the emotions expressed by individuals in today's digital world. Customers and users now have easier and faster ways to share their thoughts and

5. CONCLUSION

The proposed Sentiment Analysis (SA) model will be developed and implemented in Python, and its performance will be thoroughly evaluated. The results will be compared with those of conventional models using Type I positive performance metrics, including Accuracy, Sensitivity, Specificity, Precision, Negative Predictive Value (NPV), F1-Score, and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC). In addition, Type II negative performance metrics such as False Positive Rate (FPR), False Negative Rate (FNR), and False Discovery Rate (FDR) will also be used for comparison.

REFERENCES

- [1] Guangyu Mu, Li Dai, Xiurong Li, Xiaoqing Ju, Ying Chen and Jiaxiu Dai, "DIBTBL: A Novel Text Sentiment Analysis Model Based on an Improved Swarm Intelligence Algorithm and Deep Learning," IEEE Access, vol. 12, pp. 158669-158684, 2024.
- [2] Putta Durga and Deepthi Godavarthi, "Deep-Sentiment: An Effective Deep Sentiment Analysis Using a Decision-Based Recurrent Neural Network (D-RNN)," IEEE Access, vol. 11, pp. 108433-108447, 2023.
- [3] Jie Yu and Chunhong Qi, "Machine Learning-Based Sentiment Analysis in English Literature: Using Deep Learning Models to Analyze Emotional and Thematic Content in Texts," IEEE Access, vol. 13, pp. 65997-66008, 2025.
- [4] B. Valarmathia, N. Srinivasa Gupta, V. Karthick, T.Chellatamiland, K. Santhie and Dhanush Chalicheemalaf, "Sentiment Analysis of Covid-19 Twitter Data using Deep Learning Algorithm" Procedia Computer Science, Vol. 235, Pages 3397-3407,2024.
- [5] Tanjim Mahmud, Rezaul Karim, Rishita Chakma, Tanjia Chowdhury, Mohammad Shahadat Hossain and Karl Andersson f, "A Benchmark Dataset for Cricket Sentiment Analysis in Bangla Social Media Text" Procedia Computer Science, Vol. 238, Pages 377-384,2024.
- [6] Hendri Murfi, Syamsyuriani, Theresia Gowandi, Gianinna Ardanewari and Siti Nurrohmah, "BERT-based combination of convolutional and recurrent neural network for Indonesian sentiment analysis" Applied Soft Computing, Vol. 151,2024.
- [7] Roshy Thomas and J. R. Jeba," A novel framework for an intelligent deep learning-based product recommendation system using sentiment analysis (SA)," Automatika, vol 65:2, pp 410-424, 2024.
- [8] Bellar, O., Baina, A. and Ballafkih, " M. Sentiment Analysis: Predicting Product Reviews for E-Commerce Recommendations Using Deep Learning and Transformers" Mathematics, vol 12, pp 2403, 2024.
- [9] M. A. El-Affendi, K. Alrajhi and A. Hussain, "A Novel Deep Learning-Based Multilevel Parallel Attention Neural (MPAN) Model for Multidomain Arabic Sentiment Analysis," IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 7508-7518, 2021.
- [10] M. A. El-Affendi, K. Alrajhi and A. Hussain, "A Novel Deep Learning-Based Multilevel Parallel Attention Neural (MPAN) Model for Multidomain Arabic Sentiment Analysis," IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 7508-7518, 2021.
- [11] M. Yekrangi and N. S. Nikolov, "Domain-Specific Sentiment Analysis: An Optimized Deep Learning Approach for the Financial Markets," IEEE Access, vol. 11, pp. 70248-70262, 2023.
- [12] A. Sherin, I. Jasmine Selvakumari Jeya and S. N. Deepa, "Enhanced Aquila Optimizer Combined Ensemble Bi-LSTM-GRU With Fuzzy Emotion Extractor for Tweet Sentiment Analysis and Classification," IEEE Access, vol. 12, pp. 141932-141951, 2024.
- [13] K. Jahanbin and M. A. Z. Chahooki, "Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis of Twitter Influencers to Predict the Trend of Cryptocurrencies Based on Hybrid Deep Transfer Learning Models," IEEE Access, vol. 11, pp. 121656-121670, 2023.
- [14] S. Eyvazi-Abdoljabbar, S. Kim, M. -R. Feizi-Derakhshi, Z. Farhadi and D. Abdulameer Mohammed, "An Ensemble-Based Model for Sentiment Analysis of Persian Comments on Instagram Using Deep Learning Algorithms," IEEE Access, vol. 12, pp. 151223-151235, 2024.
- [15] F. Huang, X. Li, C. Yuan, S. Zhang, J. Zhang and S. Qiao, "Attention-Emotion-Enhanced Convolutional LSTM for Sentiment Analysis," IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems, vol. 33, no. 9, pp. 4332-4345, Sept. 2022.
- [16] H. Studiawan, F. Sohel and C. Payne, "Anomaly Detection in Operating System Logs with Deep Learning-Based Sentiment Analysis," IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 2136-2148, 2021.
- [17] U. Naqvi, A. Majid and S. A. Abbas, "UTSA: Urdu Text Sentiment Analysis Using Deep Learning Methods," IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 114085-114094, 2021.
- [18] M. A. El-Affendi, K. Alrajhi and A. Hussain, "A Novel Deep Learning-Based Multilevel Parallel Attention Neural (MPAN) Model for Multidomain Arabic Sentiment Analysis," IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 7508-7518, 2021.
- [19] V. D. Prabha and R. Rathipriya, "Competitive Capsule Network Based Sentiment Analysis on Twitter COVID-19 Vaccines," Journal of Web Engineering, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 1583-1601, July 2022.
- [20] H. Shuqin and R. C. Raga, "A Deep Learning Model for Student Sentiment Analysis on Course Reviews," IEEE Access, vol. 12, pp. 136747-136758, 2024.
- [21] A. Maroof, S. Wasi, S. I. Jami and M. S. Siddiqui, "Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Service Industry," IEEE Access, vol. 12, pp. 109702-109713, 2024.
- [22] Qianwen Ariel Xu, Chrisina Jayne and Victor Chang, " An emoji feature-incorporated multi-view deep learning for explainable sentiment classification of social

- media reviews," *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Vol. 202, 2024.
- [23] K. L. Tan, C. P. Lee, K. M. Lim and K. S. M. Anbananthen, "Sentiment Analysis With Ensemble Hybrid Deep Learning Model," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 103694-103704, 2022.
- [24] İ. Aygün, B. Kaya and M. Kaya, "Aspect Based Twitter Sentiment Analysis on Vaccination and Vaccine Types in COVID-19 Pandemic With Deep Learning," *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 2360-2369, May 2022.
- [25] Mohammed Hussein Abdalla, Jafar Majidpour, Rahela Aziz Rasul, Abdulrahman A. Alsewari, Tarik Ahmed Rashid and Aram Mahmood Ahmed, "Sentiment Analysis Based on Hybrid Neural Network Techniques Using Binary Coordinate Ascent Algorithm," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 134087-134099, 2023.
- [26] Sarada Mohapatra and Prabhujit Mohapatra, "American zebra optimization algorithm for global optimization problems," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 13, no. 5211, 2023.